

Panel discussion: Cultural challenges of user research in Americas

**Leandro Miletto
Tonetto^{1,2}**
ltonetto@gmail.com

Dilan Mahendran³
dilan.mahendran@gmail.com

¹*Unisinos, Brazil*

²*Zooma – Consumer
Experience, Brazil*

³*Dropbox, United States
of America*

Topic Design practice and user research have a close and polemic relationship. It is known that user research may play the role of providing information that allows insights during the design process. On the other hand, professionals commonly report that structured data can limit creativity, or do not believe that the observation of everyday life can feed them novel and meaningful insights. This is common to observe, since the industry frequently uses design research to control risks, e.g. to maximize the chances of success of a product, rather than looking for creative insights. In America, researchers deal with many challenges to understand user experience. In addition to the known turbulent relationship between user research and design, many cultural issues also need to be addressed: users from distinct backgrounds express differently about their experiences due to cultural disparities that interfere in the way they express emotions; the market often tends to traditional uses of research, such as risk control; and many creative designers may feel oppressed when working with design guidelines that come from research. In this session, organizers report a series of experiences in Americas that facilitate the understanding of how to work with user research in this diverse continent.

Purpose This session explores how user research has been used by companies in Latin and North America, as well as the challenges encountered in dealing with diverse cultural backgrounds. It provides attendants the opportunity to understand the gap between how this discipline could contribute to design practices and how it is actually being incorporated in everyday practice of organizations, including how to address user diversity in these projects. The main purpose of this special session is to allow a critical view on the topic, reducing the bridge between academia and industry, based on actual and current market experiences.

Keywords *User research in Americas, Design research, Design practice, Relationship between user research and design, Cultural issues in design research*